

The Effect of Injection of Autologous Nanofat for Scar Rejuvenation – A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract

Background: The current study's aim was to assess the effect of injection of autologous nanofat among patients requesting for rejuvenation of scar less than 5 years duration.

Methods: This research was done as a prospective observational study from April 2021 to March 2022 including 14 patients who attended Plastic Surgery OPD of a tertiary care centre for scar rejuvenation and were treated with autologous nanofat injection.

Results: The Patient and Observer Scar Assessment Scale was utilized to evaluate each patient. Following the surgery, both the patient and the observer's total Patient and Observer Scar Assessment Scale scores (namely, the average score of 6 items) considerably dropped, which is consistent with an improvement in scar quality.

Conclusions: Autologous nanofat injection is a safe, easy, reliable option for scar rejuvenation especially for scars less than 5 years of duration.

Categories: Plastic Surgery, Transplantation

Keywords: Posas, Adipose Derived Stem Cells, Nanofat, Scar Rejuvenation, Autologous Fat Grafting.

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Introduction

Wound is something that is commonly faced by surgeons. Wound healing process results in the formation of scars. When scars occur in exposed areas of our body, they become a source of embarrassment and psychological trauma to the concerned person. Plastic Surgeons need to face the request for the removal of scars in their daily practice. Even though it seems to be an easy procedure for the patient, scar revision is actually a challenge. Several techniques are currently in practice for scar revision.

Fat grafting is a technique that has many benefits in different areas of Plastic surgery. Nanofat grafting is a newer technique introduced in 2013 by Tonnard. After manually emulsifying and filtering the extracted fat, a liquid suspension known as nanofat was produced.[1] Nanofat did not contain any viable adipocytes, but they were rich in adipose-derived stem cells which gives it a regenerative potential. Hence nanofat was used for scar rejuvenation in our study.

Materials and Methods

A prospective observational study of 14 patients who underwent nanofat grafting for scar rejuvenation in the Plastic Surgery department of Government Medical College Thiruvananthapuram, from April 2021 to March 2022 was done. The research included both females and males with scars from different etiologies who were between the ages of 12 and 80. Patients with an unstable scar, the scar of more than 5 years duration, malignancies, active skin infections, keloidal tendencies, oral steroid, isotretinoin or anticoagulant therapy, pregnancy, contractures, patients with severe cardiovascular disorder, diseases like SLE, porphyrias, metabolic and systemic disorders, bleeding disorders were excluded from the study.

The preformed questionnaire was filled out for all cases which include details about the scar like scar location, age of injury, mechanism of injury, history of contamination, type of healing, and comorbidities of the patient.

POSAS was used for the evaluation of scars.[2] The lead investigator scored the preoperative POSAS observer scale, and the patient scored the patient scale while being supervised by the investigator. For every instance, photographic documentation was also completed. The patient scale had a total minimum and maximum score of 6 and 60, respectively. By comparing the total patient score as well as the total observer score on the POSAS scale between preoperative and postoperative times, the aesthetic outcome of the scar was evaluated.

Procedure

Under tumescent anaesthesia and with the utmost aseptic care, the nanofat grafting was carried out. In all instances, the lower abdomen wall was the location from which the fat was aspirated utilising a syringe liposuction procedure using a 1.75 mm Colemans cannula and a 10cc Leur Lock syringe. After being sealed with a hypodermic needle to prevent leaking, the aspirated fat was left undisturbed for 10 to 15 minutes in a vertical posture in a 200ml sterile steel tumbler. The tumescent fluid

that had separated from the aspirate was thrown away. Using 2 10cc Leur Lock syringes coupled by a three-way connection, the supernatant fat had been emulsified into a milky white emulsion over the course of 30-35 passes. To further sift the emulsion and guarantee free passage via a 1-inch, 27G needle, we used a 2-layered wet saline surgical gauze. After filtration, the resultant fluid was injected intralesionally into the scar with a 1 inch, 27G needle and insulin syringe. The injection's endpoint is identified by a scar that has a yellowish blanching. Patients were advised not to vigorously rub the scar for 12 hours and not to take aspirin or other anti-inflammatory drugs while on treatment. No dressing will be required. The scar was reevaluated after three and six months. Prior to surgery and six months following injection, scar evaluation was done using the POSAS score. Photographs were taken preoperatively and six months after injection. The decision for repeated injection with emulsified fat after an interval of 6 months, was taken according to the response of scar and patient preference.

Figure 1: Technique of nanofat injection (A) syringe liposuction (B) separation of fat (C) emulsification (D) filtration with a moist saline gauze (E) nanofat injection into scar

Results

Questionnaire details like scar location, age of injury, mechanism of injury, history of contamination, type of healing, and habitual smoking were analyzed and tabulated.

Six male and eight female patients made up the study's total of 14 participants. Mean age of the

study population was 21, the minimum and maximum age was 11 and 32, respectively. The majority of scars were on the neck region and head and rest on the upper limb. Most scars came under the duration of 48 - 60 months. Most common mode of injury was burns. History of contamination was present in most cases. Out of 14 cases, 9 cases healed by secondary intention. Habitual smoking history was present in 4 cases.

Table 1: Scar location, age and mechanism of injury, contamination, type of healing, habitual smoking are tabulated

Scar Location	Age of Injury	Mechanism of Injury	Contamination	Type of Healing	Habitual Smoking
head and neck -11	24- 36 months - 3	RTA - 4	present - 11	primary intention - 5	present - 4
upper limb - 3	36 - 48 months - 4	Post-Surgical - 3	absent - 3	secondary intention - 9	absent - 10
	48 - 60 months -7	post burns - 7			
RTA - road traffic accidents					

POSAS patient score

reduced to 9 postoperatively. Maximum preoperative score was 39, which was reduced to 32 postoperatively.

POSAS patient score analysis shows that the minimum preoperative score was 14, which was

Table 2: Analysis of POSAS patient score preoperatively and postoperatively

POSAS Patient Score	Number of Patients	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean	Standard Deviation
Pre procedure	14	14	39	28.21	8.5770
Post procedure	14	9	32	22.42	7.7926

Evaluation of different variables of POSAS patient score like itching, pain, colour, stiffness,

irregularity, and thickness showed that thickness and stiffness showed significant improvement when compared to improvement in pain and itching.

Figure 2: Chart representation of change in variables in POSAS patient score before and after the procedure

POSAS observer score

reduced to 12 postoperatively. Maximum preoperative score was 49, which was reduced to 44 postoperatively.

POSAS observer score analysis shows that the minimum preoperative score was 20, which was

Table 3: Analysis of POSAS observer score preoperatively and postoperatively

POSAS Observer Score	Number of Patients	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean	Standard Deviation
Pre procedure	14	20	49	33.92	9.4091
Post procedure	14	12	44	28.35	9.3447

Evaluation of different variables of POSAS observer score like pigmentation, vascularity, relief, thickness, surface area and pliability showed that

thickness and pliability showed significant improvement when compared to improvement in surface area.

Figure 3: Chart representation of changes in variables in POSAS observer score before and after the procedure

Overall POSAS Score: POSAS score analysis of all patients showed that mean patient score reduced

from 28 to 22 and mean observer score reduced from 33 to 28.

Table 4: Analysis of overall POSAS score

Variable	Pre-Test Mean ± sd	Post Test Mean ± sd	P value (Paired t test)
POSAS - Patient	28.21±8.57	22.43±7.793	0.0001
POSAS - Observer	33.93±9.40	28.36±9.34	0.0001

Examples

Case 1: 12-year-old girl with post-burn scar on right cheek of 4 years duration. She underwent

autologous nanofat injection. The patient score went from 31 to 24 while the observer score went from 31 to 25.

Figure 4: Pre-operative (A) and post-operative (B) photographs after injection of autologous emulsified fat in post-burns facial scar

Case 2: 18-year-old female exhibited with post-burn scar right cheek of 4 years duration. She was given nanofat injection therapy. The patient score

improved from 39 to 32 and the observer score from 44 to 38.

Case 3: 16-year-old male displayed post scald burn scar right cheek of 3 years duration and underwent au-tologous nanofat injection. Significant

improvement was seen with the patient score improving from 39 to 32 and the observer score from 34 to 28.

Case 4: A 32-year-old male presented with post-traumatic scar right angle of the mandible of 2 years duration, experienced autologous nanofat injection.

There was significant scar improvement with patient score improvement from 37 to 29 and observer score improvement from 44 to 36.

Figure 7: Pre-operative (A) and post-operative (B) photographs after injection of autologous emulsified fat in post-traumatic scar

Discussion

The role of fat auto-transplantation in plastic surgery ranges from simple volume augmentation to regenerative medicine. When tuberculous osteitis caused a sunken region of the face, Neuber (1893) first described fat transplantation using small pieces of upper arm fat to restore facial contouring.[3] We didn't start to comprehend and advance the predictability of fat grafting until Lyndon Peer investigated the gross and microscopic appearance of transplanted fat in the 1950s.[4] A variety of cell types, including adipose-derived stem cells with a proliferative capability that is comparable to mesenchymal cells, make up the active, dynamic tissue known as fat.

ADSCs ("Adipose-Derived Stem Cells") are multipotent progenitor cells that Zuk et al. introduced in 2001.[5] After radiation treatment, the ability of ADSC to regenerate tissue was initially documented by Rigotti et al. (2007).[6] With hydration and neo-angiogenesis, they observed that lesions that had previously been irreversible showed improvement. After that, Klinger et al. (2008) reported the first usage of AFG ("Autologous Fat Graft") for the treatment of scars.[7] 3 patients with burns to the hands, face, limbs, and trunk were treated with 2 sessions of AFG and checked on 6 months later in this case series. An advantageous effect was seen with reduction in scar tissue thickness, improved texture, and more softness.

In a 2015 experiment, Zhang et al. intralesionally injected adipose tissue-derived stem cells into ears of rabbit and showed that this decreased the development of hypertrophic scarring by lowering the expression of the genes for alpha-SMA and

collagen type I and increasing collagen deposition.[8] In a mouse model, fat grafting was done to irradiated skin, and post-treatment histological and photometrical analyses were carried out.[9] It has been shown that fat grafting improves collagen organisation and reduces radiation-induced fibrosis.

Tonnard et al. first used the term 'nanofat' in 2013 to describe a novel technique for preparing autologous fat that focuses primarily on its regeneration characteristics.[1] They examined the viability of adipocytes as well as the quantity and activity of ADSCs in comparison to lipoaspirates collected using conventional methods for fat harvesting. Three fat samples were examined in the study. Initially, they had a standard lipoaspirate sample (macrofat). Microfat was used in the second sample, which was obtained via a multiport small-hole cannula. The third was nanofat created by processing microfat. The lipoaspirate underwent emulsification and filtration as part of the processing. The state of the adipocytes in fat samples was examined. In the nanofat sample, no adipocytes that were still alive were found. The nanofat sample still contained a significant amount of ADSCs. The stem cells from the three samples were equally capable of proliferating and differentiating in cell cultures. Six months after surgery, clinical applications revealed remarkably improved skin quality. No granulomas, infections, fat cysts, or other unfavourable side effects were noticed.

In 2017, Uyulmaz et al studied the impact of nanofat grafting on wrinkles, scars, and skin discoloration among 52 patients, out of which 48 were highly satisfied with the results.[10] Their findings

demonstrate that nanofat has favourable impacts on skin texture and aesthetic appeal.

According to a 2018 study published in the Indian Journal of Plastic Surgery by Bhooshan et al, "Autologous emulsified fat injection for rejuvenation of scars: A prospective observational study," autologous emulsified nanofat injection is a simple, daycare surgical procedure for scar rejuvenation with few risks and high patient compliance.[11] All sorts of scars, especially those with a short duration, have their symptoms and texture improved. The research is distinctive in that the patient's assessment of the scar is also evaluated and compared to the post-operative outcomes, thereby eliminating observer bias from the final outcome. Atrophic hyperpigmented long-lasting scars exhibited less recovery with nanofat injection, according to this research.

The different methods that are in practice for scar treatment are surgical scar revision, compression garment therapy, silicone gel sheet application, corticosteroid injection, laser, chemical peel, dermabrasion etc. A second scar is produced during surgical scar revision, which may or may not result in positive outcomes and places additional physical, emotional, and financial strain on the patient.[12] Compression treatment and silicone gel sheets need to be used for longer periods of time in order to provide greater outcomes; this necessitates patient cooperation and is also expensive. Corticosteroid injection has many disadvantages such as atrophy of subcutaneous tissue, hypopigmentation, skin atrophy and severe pain on injection. Higher doses can also contribute to systemic side effects like altered blood glucose levels, menstrual irregularities etc. The different modalities of non-surgical rejuvenation like laser produce tissue destruction and reepithelialisation.

Nanofat is cost-effective therapy. It uses the rejuvenating properties of ADSC to bring about scar changes. It does not require any postoperative scar care therapies. Since the fat being injected is autologous, nanofat injection has no systemic side effects. In 2 weeks, localised effects like swelling will go away as the emulsified fat is absorbed. There is no tissue destruction or immunogenic reactions or hypersensitivity here. The procedure involved in fat harvesting and processing into nanofat and injecting into scar has a flat learning curve. It can be done under local anaesthesia as a daycare procedure. Since fat is harvested with a 1.75mm cannula and injected using a 27G needle, no sutures and thereby no suture removal is needed.

The study considered the patient's opinion regarding the scar also in addition to the observer's opinion by using the POSAS scoring system. In this study, it was noted that thickness, pliability, stiffness etc showed more improvement than surface area. A

modest sample size was used in the investigation, which was done in a single tertiary care facility. Therefore, multicentric randomised control trials will be needed for the findings in large samples to be validated.

Conclusions

Autologous nanofat injection is a cost-effective, easily learnt scar rejuvenation procedure with minimal complications. It is a useful daycare procedure that can be used for scars of all kinds of etiologies.

Additional Information

Disclosures

Human Subjects: Consent was obtained or waived by all participants in this study. Human Ethics Committee, Medical College, Thiruvananthapuram issued approval 03/14/2021/MCT. Decision of the HEC/IRB - Recommended.

Animal Subjects: All authors have confirmed that this study did not involve animal subjects or tissue.

Conflicts of Interest: In compliance with the ICMJE uniform disclosure form, all authors declare the following:

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